

Supporting Information

Responsive Soft Interface Liquid Crystal Microfluidics

Ayşe Nurcan Özşahin and Emre Bukusoglu*

Department of Chemical Engineering, Middle East Technical University, Dumlupınar Bulvarı
No.1 Çankaya, Ankara, 06800 Türkiye.

Video S1. 5CB filling in a 2-inlet channel. The stable LC-water soft interface was maintained as 5CB was flowing along the hydrophobic pathway during the simultaneous flow of 5CB and pure water with the same inlet pressure of $P_{\text{inlet}}=100$ mbar, after surface treatment with DMOAP and pure water introduction to the system. The filling process occurred similarly to the example polarized optical micrographs shown in Fig. 1d (i) and (ii), without rupturing the virtual wall at the boundary of the DMOAP and bare glass surface. In this case, we observed bright colors on the 5CB side since the mesogens were aligned with the flow, consistent with strong flow regime conditions under polarized optical microscopy with cross polarizers oriented at 135° and 45° . Scale bar: 100 μm

Video S2. 5CB filling in a 3-inlet channel. The stable LC-water soft interface was maintained in a 3-inlet channel. 5CB was flowing along the hydrophobic path during the simultaneous flow of 5CB and pure water phases with the same inlet pressures ($P_{\text{inlet}}=100$ mbar) in Aq.-LC-Aq. arrangement. The virtual walls were stable continuously along the channel while 5CB was filling. The video was collected under a polarized optical microscope with a polarizer and an analyzer oriented 135° and 45° , respectively. Scale bar: 100 μm

Video S3. (i) Flow in a microchannel with a bare glass surface. The inner surfaces of a 2-inlet channel surfaces were not functionalized by using DMOAP and maintained as bare glass surfaces. Thus, hydrophilic properties were present homogeneously along the channel. After the introduction of 5CB and pure water, the two phases did not form a stable interface, and a stable flow was not maintained. The video starts with $P_{\text{LC,inlet}}=85$ mbar, and $P_{\text{water,inlet}}=30$ mbar, and at the second of 13.5, $P_{\text{LC,inlet}}$ was decreased to 30 mbar to have the same inlet pressure values. However, the flow was not maintained in a stable form. This highlights the significance of the presence of hydrophobic and hydrophilic properties for a stable LC-water interface. **(ii)** 5CB flow in a microchannel with a homogeneous DMOAP-coated surface. We coated the inner surfaces of a 2-inlet channel with DMOAP; thus, the surfaces became homogeneously hydrophobic. The video shows 5CB flow individually in the microchannel to exhibit the homogeneity of coating, and it was flowing through hard interfaces with an inlet pressure of $P_{\text{inlet}}=60$ mbar. **(iii)** Flow in a microchannel with a homogeneous DMOAP surface. Similar to (ii), the inner surfaces of a 2-inlet channel were functionalized with DMOAP without introducing pure water into the system while coating. When we introduced pure water and 5CB to the channel with the same inlet pressure, we could not maintain a stable interface between the two phases, since surfaces were homogeneously hydrophobic. We observed sequential slugs of 5CB and aqueous during flow starting at the junction point of the microchannel as can be

seen in the video. The inlet pressure for both phases was 100 mbar. These videos were collected under a polarized optical microscope with cross polarizers oriented at 135° and 45° . Scale bar: $100\ \mu\text{m}$

Video S4. Stable flow in 2-inlet channels. After obtaining a stable LC-water soft interface, we achieved controlling the flow inside the channel by rupturing the interface and returning to the stable state. Starting pressures for both phases were the same ($P_{\text{inlet}}=120$ mbar), then, $P_{\text{LC,inlet}}$ was increased to 200 mbar and the rupture can be seen directly from the video. When pressures were equalized ($P_{\text{inlet}}=120$ mbar), the interface returned to the stable state. The stable soft interface boundary (hydrophobic-hydrophilic side boundary) can be directly seen when LC crossed over the boundary and it was flowing along both sides. Cross-polarizers were oriented at 135° and 45° in a polarized optical microscope for imaging. Scale bar: $100\ \mu\text{m}$

Video S5. Color change in 5CB bulk side due to inlet pressure and velocity change. In this case, we observed color transitions which were related to the angle change with the flow direction due to increasing velocity in a 3-inlet channel. The flow arrangement was Aq.-Aq.-LC and, the inlet pressures of these phases were increased simultaneously from 15 mbar to 50 mbar within 70 seconds. The transition from dark to bright colors, and then, bright to higher-order interference colors can be correlated with Michel-Levy interference colors. Cross-polarizers were oriented at 135° and 45° in a polarized optical microscope for imaging. Scale bar: $100\ \mu\text{m}$

Video S6. Response to shear in a 3-inlet channel. The stable LC-water soft interfaces in a 3-inlet channel were observed during the changing velocity values of one of the water phases. In the beginning, 5CB was flowing along the hydrophobic pathway during the simultaneous flow of 5CB and pure water phases with the same inlet pressure ($P_{\text{inlet}}=5$ mbar). The virtual wall was stable and continued along the channel. Maintaining the inlet pressures of one of the pure water sides (seen above in the video) and 5CB at constant, the inlet pressure of the second pure water was increased with a ramp of 5 mbar to 100 mbar in 120 seconds. Continuously, its pressure was decreased by following the same path backward. After the soft interface was ruptured totally, it returned to the beginning state where both the water and LC sides had the same inlet pressure. The video was collected under a polarized optical microscope with a polarizer and an analyzer oriented at 135° and 45° , respectively. Scale bar: $100\ \mu\text{m}$

Video S7. Interface rupture due to chemical change in aqueous phase. After obtaining a stable LC-water soft interface, we altered the aqueous side by SDS solutions. In the video, 1.0 mM SDS solution and 5CB flow were simultaneously continuing. However, we observed the interface rupture after introducing a 1.0 mM SDS solution. The simultaneous flow of 5CB and solution had the same inlet pressures ($P_{\text{inlet}}=60$ mbar). This was related to the durability of the soft interface against chemical changes in the aqueous phase (durability which was directly dependent on DMOAP coating). 5CB expanded through the aqueous side by rupturing the soft interface since the LC-water interface was not resistant to SDS presence. The video also shows how the DMOAP surface and bare glass surface differed when 5CB flows through both sides. Thus, the unstable flow of phases was not related to the inner surface chemistry as hydrophilic and hydrophobic pathways but the DMOAP to glass transition at the interface in this case. Cross-polarizers were oriented at 135° and 45° in a polarized optical microscope for imaging. Scale bar: $100\ \mu\text{m}$

Figure S1. Photograph of the microfluidic channel platform under the used microscope setup. The two tubings were introduced to the system as Nile Red+5CB mixture (colored one), and water (non-colored one) for a two-inlet channel. The pressure at the inlet was set with microfluidic pumps.

Figure S2. Polarized optical micrographs of LC bulk and interface with respect to the rotation of the crossed polarizer. Scale bars: 50 μm

About Fig. S2: At low pressure, we observed complete dark appearances of the LC phase when cross polarizers oriented at $90^\circ\text{-}0^\circ$ and $135^\circ\text{-}45^\circ$. From the collected polarized optical micrographs with angles increasing by 10° , we observed dark imaging for all cases at $P_{\text{inlet}} = 10$ mbar. This indicated the perpendicular LC orientation to the imaging plane.

Figure S3. Optical micrographs of 5CB flowing in a 2-inlet channel that is in contact with an aqueous phase of **(a)** pure water, **(b)** 0.1 mM SDS, **(c)** 0.5 mM SDS, and **(d)** 1.0 mM SDS. *(i)* and *(ii)* show the polarized optical micrographs with the orientation of cross polarizers as 135°-45° and 90°-0°, respectively. *(iii)* FCPM images were collected with the polarization angle of 0° (top row) and 90° (bottom row). 5CB and aqueous phase flows were maintained at the equal inlet pressures at the indicated values. Scale bar: (i, ii) 100 μm , (iii) 20 μm .

About Fig. S3: 5CB is known to maintain planar anchoring at pure water interfaces, homeotropic anchoring at 1.0 mM SDS concentrations and tilted anchoring at intermediated SDS concentrations.¹ The micrographs show how the orientation of 5CB at such interfaces is influenced during the co-flow of 5CB and the aqueous phase.

References

1. Gupta, J. K. & Abbott, N. L. Principles for manipulation of the lateral organization of aqueous-soluble surface-active molecules at the liquid crystal - aqueous interface. *Langmuir* **25**, 2026–2033 (2009).